

Extractive spectrophotometric determination and sequential separation of palladium(II) and nickel(II) with isonitrosoacetoacetanilide

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A method has been developed for the extractive spectrophotometric determination of Pd^{II} and Ni^{II} and their sequential separation with isonitrosoacetoacetanilide (HINAcAn). It forms an orange coloured complex with Pd^{II} which is extractable in chloroform below pH 2.0 and in 0.1–2.0 N H₂SO₄ and has absorption maximum at 420 nm. Ni^{II} forms a yellow coloured complex which is extractable in chloroform in the pH range 7.0–8.0, the absorption maximum being at 405 nm. Beer's law is obeyed over the ranges 0.5–7.0 ppm for Pd and 0.4–6.0 ppm for Ni. The nature of the two complexes has been discussed. The method has also been applied for the analysis of synthetic mixtures and real samples.

Various reagents have been used for the spectrophotometric determination of palladium¹. However, many of these methods suffer from certain limitations like interference by common metal ions, heating for complex formation, alkaline working medium and also pH control. However this reagent does not involve rigid control of pH and sensitivity is also quite comparable. In the present communication isonitrosoacetoacetanilide (HINAcAn) has been proposed as a new analytical reagent for the extraction, sequential separation and subsequent spectrophotometric determination of Pd^{II} and Ni^{II}.

Results and Discussion

The absorption spectra of Pd^{II}-HINAcAn and Ni^{II}-HINAcAn complexes in chloroform show maximum absorbance at 420 and 405 nm respectively. Optimum extraction of Pd^{II} is obtained below pH 2.0 and in 0.1–2.0 N H₂SO₄ and that of Ni^{II} in the range 7.0–8.0. Equilibration time of 30 s and 10 min gave quantitative extraction of Pd^{II} and Ni^{II} respectively. Chloroform was found to be the best solvent for both the systems. The colours of the organic phase containing Pd^{II}-HINAcAn and Ni^{II}-HINAcAn complexes were stable for more than 72 and 48 h respectively. Beer's law was found to be valid over concentration ranges 0.5–7.0 ppm of Pd^{II} and 0.4–6.0 ppm of Ni^{II}. Molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity for Pd^{II} were found to be 7186 dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹ and 0.014 µg ml⁻¹ cm⁻² respectively; the respective values for Ni^{II} were 1408 dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹ and 0.040 µg ml⁻¹ cm⁻².

In interference study, 50 µg of Pd and 100 µg of Ni were taken and the tolerance limit for the foreign ion was taken as the amount required to cause an error of not more than ±2% in the recovery of the metal ion. In case of Pd^{II} determination, 20 mg of Ag^I, Ba^{II}, Th^I, Zn^{II}, Hg^{II}, U^{VI}, Zr^{IV}, Bi^{III}, Cd^{II}, Be^{II}; 10 mg of Ni^{II}, Sn^{II}, Pb^{II}, Mg^{II}, Cu^{II}, Li^I, Tl^I, Ru^{III}, Al^{III}, Cl⁻, SO₄²⁻, S₂O₈²⁻, IO₃⁻, ClO₃⁻, NO₃⁻, NO₂⁻, BrO₃⁻,

urea, citrate, acetate; 5 mg of Te^{IV}, V^V, W^{VI}, F⁻; 2 mg of Cr^{III}, Co^{II}, Mo^{VI}; 1 mg of Pt^{IV}, Ir^{IV}, Rh^{III}, Mn^{II}; 0.5 mg of Sr^{II}, PO₄³⁻ and 0.1 mg of Os^{IV} were tolerated. Fe^{III} and Sb^{III} were masked with NaF, I⁻ and Br⁻ with Hg(NO₃)₂, thiourea and EDTA with CuSO₄, and S₂O₃²⁻ and SCN⁻ were removed by boiling with HNO₃ before extraction. In the estimation of Ni^{II}, 10 mg of Ag^I, Li^I, Mg^{II}, Ca^{II}, Zn^{II}, Bi^{III}, As^{III}, Mo^{VI}, Cl⁻, I⁻, F⁻, SO₄²⁻, S₂O₃²⁻, S₂O₈²⁻, SO₃²⁻, SCN⁻, NO₂⁻, NO₃⁻, PO₄³⁻, urea, thiourea, tartarate, acetate; 5 mg of Pb^{II}, Sn^{II}, Sr^{II}, W^{VI}, IO₃⁻, ClO₃⁻; 2 mg of Mn^{II}, Cr^{III}, Al^{III}, Ce^{IV}, BrO₃⁻, Br⁻, oxalate, citrate; 1 mg of Cd^{II}; 0.5 mg of Ru^{III}, Pt^{IV} and 0.1 mg of Fe^{II} and Fe^{III} did not interfere. Sb^{III} and Zr^{IV} interfered and were masked with NaF. Pd^{II} was masked with NH₄SCN, Cu^{II} with Na₂S₂O₃, Os^{IV} with thiourea and EDTA with excess of CaCl₂.

Composition of the extracted Pd^{II}-HINAcAn complex determined by Job's continuous variation method and mole-ratio method revealed 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 M : L ratio, indicating the probable composition to be Pd(INAcAn)⁺ and Pd(INAcAn)₂. It may be inferred that species exhibits 1 : 2 ratio on further addition of reagent. Thus the extracted species can be formulated as Pd(INAcAn)₂. The nature of the Pd^{II} complex was further confirmed by ion-exchange method and conductometric method which also supported the above inference. The slope-ratio method was employed to study the nature of Ni^{II}-HINAcAn and it was found to exhibit 1 : 2 metal-to-ligand ratio.

The proposed methods were applied for the estimation of the two metals in various synthetic mixtures and some standard samples. Samples like Pd-charcoal catalyst for Pd^{II} and stainless steel and Ni–Al alloy for Ni^{II} were analysed and the results obtained were in good agreement with the reported values.

The method developed for the separation and estima-

tion of Pd^{II} and Ni^{II} was utilised for their sequential separation and the results obtained show that the method can be successfully employed for the sequential separation and estimation of Pd^{II} and Ni^{II}.

Experimental

A Bausch and Lomb Spectronic-20 spectrophotometer was used. pH was measured using a Elico LI-120 pH-meter. Stock solutions of Pd^{II} and Ni^{II} were prepared by dissolving their respective salts in distilled water (few drops of H₂SO₄, added in sulphate salt of Ni^{II}) and standardised gravimetrically by dimethyl glyoxime method. The reagent HINAcAn was prepared from acetoacetanilide by the reported method².

Procedure : Experimental procedure was the same as

described earlier³. Pd^{II} and Ni^{II} were estimated by standard methods.

References

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